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Title:

Appropriateness in the prescription of antiplatelet therapy in patients attending a medical clinic in a primary medical care unit in Sri Lanka and its unwarranted burden on the institutional pharmaceutical budget

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Keywords: *Antiplatelet therapy, medication review, guideline recommendations, high bleeding risk*

ABSTRACT

Background: Antiplatelet agents are commonly prescribed for the primary and secondary prevention of cardiovascular disease. The recent guideline updates have refined the indications for antiplatelet therapy to optimise patient care. However, due to lack of medication review this has not translated into practice. Inappropriate prescriptions of antiplatelet agents thus observed are a health risk for patients and unnecessary financial burden on the healthcare system.

Objective: To assess the appropriateness in prescription of antiplatelet therapy in patients attending an outpatient medical clinic in a primary medical care unit in Sri Lanka and its unwarranted burden on the institutional pharmaceutical budget.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted on patients attending the medical clinic in a primary medical care unit Sri Lanka. All patients who were followed up from January to December 2023 were recruited for the study. Patients who were lost to follow up, deceased and transferred/discharged from the clinic during the study period were excluded. Data were collected from patient clinic records, annual pharmaceutical estimate, stock transfer vouchers and drug stores register using data extraction sheets. The 2019 American Heart Association / American College of Cardiology guidelines was used as the reference.

Results: About total of 61/234 clinic patients were on antiplatelet therapy. Majority were elderly patients; ≥ 65 years (90%) treated for hypertension(95%), dyslipidaemia(82%), diabetes mellitus(54%) and atherosclerotic vascular disease(75.4%). Most(60.7%) were on antiplatelets for secondary prevention of cardiovascular disease. A 57.4% was on inappropriate prescriptions, mainly for primary prevention(68.6%). Nearly 53% of the budget allocated for antiplatelets was spent on inappropriate prescriptions.

Conclusion: Delay in translating guidelines to practice and lack of medication review may have caused inappropriate prescription of antiplatelet agents placing patients at undue health risks and causing a financial risk to the healthcare system. Both clinicians and administrators should bear responsibility and strive to pre-empt health hazards and associated opportunity cost.

Background

Antiplatelet agents, as implied by the name itself, are well known for the inhibition of platelet activation and aggregation which consequently reduce the risk of thrombosis and hence

thromboembolic events such as myocardial infarction and ischaemic stroke. They could be categorised according to their mechanisms of action.(1) By virtue of their mechanisms the effects they bring about are always related but not limited to inhibition of platelets. Hence the full range of indications for antiplatelet therapy is extensive and diverse.(1)

The most popular indication for antiplatelet therapy is occlusive vascular disease.(2) Dual antiplatelet therapy (DAPT) has shown considerable benefit than monotherapy in this context.(2) DAPT refers to the combination of aspirin and a P2Y12 receptor inhibitor.(3) The commonest P2Y12 receptor inhibitor used is clopidogrel. Antiplatelet therapy is used in both primary prevention and secondary prevention.(3–7)

DAPT is administered at the cost of major risk of bleeding.(3) Although the risk of bleeding is comparatively lower in monotherapy, it is not unheard of, especially in the vulnerable groups.(4) Therefore, it is vital to ensure that both monotherapy and DAPT are carried out only for the specified optimal durations and indications as recommended by guidelines, to circumvent adverse events from bleeding. Guidelines, both national and international are updated from time to time based on emerging evidence (Refer to table 1).

Table 1 - Current and Recent Guideline and Consensus Documents on Aspirin Use for the Primary Prevention of CVD(8)

Guideline	Recommendations
2012 ACCP guidelines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Suggested for adults aged ≥ 50 y without symptomatic CVD (grade 2B)
2015 AHA/ADA scientific statement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reasonable in adults with 10-y CVD risk $\geq 10\%$ and without increased risk for bleeding (ACC/AHA class IIa, LOE B; ADA grade C)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reasonable in adults with DM at intermediate risk (10-y CVD risk of 5%–10%) (ACC/AHA class IIb, LOE C; ADA grade E)
2016 ADA guidelines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consider in those with type 1 or 2 DM who are at increased CVD risk (10-y risk >10%) and are not at increased bleeding risk (grade C) Not recommended for adults with DM at low ASCVD risk (10-y risk <5%) (grade C) Clinical judgment required in patients with DM aged <50 y with other risk factors (e.g., 10-y risk of 5%–10%) (grade E)
2016 USPSTF recommendation statement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initiate in adults aged 50–59 y with 10-y CVD risk \geq10% (grade B) Individual judgment required in adults aged 60–69 y with 10-y CVD risk \geq10% (grade C) No recommendation in adults aged <50 y (grade I) No recommendation in adults aged \geq70 y (grade I)
2019 AHA/ACC guidelines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> May be considered in adults aged 40–70 y who are at higher ASCVD risk but not at increased bleeding risk (COR IIb, LOE A) Should not be used on a routine basis in adults aged >70 y (COR III, LOE B-R) Should not be used in adults of any age who are at increased risk for bleeding (COR III, LOE C-LD)

**2022 USPSTF
recommendation
statement(9)**

- For adults aged 40 to 59 years with an estimated 10% or greater 10-year cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk: The decision to initiate low-dose aspirin use for the primary prevention of CVD in this group should be an individual one. (Grade: C)
- For adults 60 years or older: Do not initiate aspirin for the primary prevention of CVD. (Grade: D)

This recommendation applies to adults 40 years or older without signs or symptoms of CVD or known CVD and who are not at increased risk for bleeding (e.g., no history of gastrointestinal ulcers, recent bleeding, or other medical conditions, or taking medications that increase bleeding risk).

ACC = American College of Cardiology; ACCP = American College of Chest Physicians; ADA = American Diabetes Association; AHA = American Heart Association; ASCVD = atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease; COR = class of recommendation; CVD = cardiovascular disease; DM = diabetes mellitus; LOE = level of evidence; USPSTF = U.S. Preventive Services Task Force.

The newer guidelines as a result may completely override the practice recommended by the previous. It is the duty of healthcare providers to stay up to date with these guidelines to optimise patient care and safety.

Despite the rapidly developing body of knowledge and evidence, there is a considerable delay in translating this knowledge to practice.(10,11) The void thus created often leads to medical

misadventures which could have been easily pre-empted by regular updating of one's knowledge on guideline recommendations and conducting medication reviews.(12)

A large number of patients followed up at medical clinics receive antiplatelet therapy.(8,13) A considerable proportion of them are elderly patients with multimorbidity and hence at high risk of bleeding.(14–16) It is therefore vital that the prescriptions of these patients are duly reviewed and optimised. Unfortunately, review and optimisation are not done effectively and inappropriate prescriptions of antiplatelets are observed.

Similar observations were made in the study setting in question; an outpatient medical clinic in a primary medical care unit in Sri Lanka.

Objectives

This study aimed to assess the appropriateness in prescription of antiplatelet therapy in patients attending an outpatient medical clinic in a primary medical care unit (PMCU) in Sri Lanka and its unwarranted burden on the institutional pharmaceutical budget.

Methods

In the context of this study, 'appropriateness' in the prescription of antiplatelet therapy referred to the adherence to 2019 American Heart Association / American College of Cardiology guidelines.

'Financial burden' referred to the proportion of the institutional pharmaceutical budget consumed by the inappropriate antiplatelet prescriptions during the study period (year 2023).

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted on patients attending the outpatient medical clinic in a primary medical care unit. All patients attending the clinic are followed up on a monthly basis. All patients followed up from January to December 2023 were recruited for the study. Patients who were lost to follow up, deceased and transferred/discharged from the clinic during the study period were excluded.

Data required were two-fold; patient-related data (demographics, prescriptions, indications, etc.) and medication-related data (quantity of consumption, price, etc.). Patient-related data were collected from clinic records by the medical officer in-charge (MOIC) of the clinic using a data extraction sheet generated on MS Excel software. Medication related data were collected from the annual drug/equipment estimate of the institution, stock transfer vouchers and the drug stores register using a separate MS Excel based data extraction sheet by the MOIC.

Risk factors for bleeding in patients on antiplatelet agents were identified during the literature review. In the literature bleeding was identified using BARC (Bleeding Academic Research Consortium) definitions across Type 0 to Type 5.(17) Patient characteristics associated with bleeding complications include older age, female sex, diabetes, hypertension, low body weight, renal impairment, smoking, history of bleeding (e.g., peptic ulcer disease) prior vascular disease, and prior stroke.(18–21) In the interest of the study older age was defined as age ≥ 65 years. Body mass index (BMI) was assessed in the place of bodyweight alone and low BMI was defined as $< 18.5\text{kg/m}^2$. There is evidence to suggest comorbidities/multimorbidity as a risk factor for bleeding.(22) Multimorbidity was defined as having 2 or more long term health conditions. Though not directly assessed in patients only on medical management for ACS on antiplatelet therapy, polypharmacy has been studied in the context of bleeding following venous thromboembolism (15), atrial fibrillation (16) and post PCI (23) establishing its risk of bleeding. The perceived bleeding risks arise from drug-drug and drug-disease interactions. The prevalence of polypharmacy in this study population was assessed to reiterate and further establish the undue medical risks the patients are exposed to due to inappropriate antiplatelet prescriptions. Polypharmacy was defined as being on 5 or more drugs for the long-term health conditions.

Descriptive statistics were used to analyse the data. MS Office Excel 2021 software was used for data analysis.

Administrative clearance was obtained from the Regional Director of Health Services, Colombo.

Results

From 234 patients on active follow up during 2023, 61 (26%) were on antiplatelet therapy. Out of 61 patients on antiplatelet therapy 49 (80%) were female. The median (IQR) age was 74 (67.5-79) years with an age range from 55-94 years. The majority 55 (90%) were elderly patients (age ≥ 65 years).

Those on monotherapy were 50 (82%) and the rest were on dual antiplatelet therapy.

The spectrum and prevalence of medical conditions treated are summarised in table 2.

Table 2 – Patient characteristics

Patient characteristic	n (%)
	N=61
Gender	
Male	12 (19.7%)
Female	49 (80.3%)
Age	
<65 years	6 (9.8%)
≥ 65 years	55 (90.2%)
Medical condition	
Hypertension	58 (95.1%)
Dyslipidaemia	50 (82.0%)
Diabetes mellitus	33 (54.1%)
Ischaemic heart disease	23 (37.7%)
Stroke	11 (18.0%)
Bronchial asthma	8 (13.1%)
Hypothyroidism	4 (6.6%)
Peripheral vascular disease	2 (3.3%)

Rheumatoid arthritis	2 (3.3%)
Osteo arthritis	2 (3.3%)
Transient ischaemic attack	1 (1.6%)
Chronic kidney disease	1 (1.6%)
Cervical spondylosis	1 (1.6%)
Seizure disorder	1 (1.6%)
Chronic liver cell disease	1 (1.6%)

The majority 37/61 (60.7%) were on antiplatelet therapy for secondary prevention of cardiovascular disease. The rest were receiving antiplatelets for primary prevention.

Multimorbidity (98.4%), hypertension (95.1%) and age \geq 65 years (90.2%) were the commonest risk factors for bleeding prevalent among patients on antiplatelet therapy (refer to table 3). Data on anaemia were insufficient and therefore not assessed. Data on body mass index were only available in some patients.

Table 3 – Prevalence of risk factors for bleeding among the patients on antiplatelet therapy

Risk factors identified	n (%)
Age \geq 65years	55 (90.2%)
Sex (female)	49 (80.3%)
Diabetes	33 (54.1%)
Hypertension	58 (95.1%)
Polypharmacy (on \geq 5 medications)	49 (80.3%)
Multimorbidity (\geq2 long-term health conditions)	60 (98.4%)
Low body mass index $<18.5 \text{ kgm}^{-2}$	Assessed only in 43 (6/43 – 14.0%)

Chronic kidney disease	1 (1.6%)
Liver disease	1 (1.6%)
Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs	5 (8.2%)

Majority 35/61 (57.4%) of the antiplatelet prescriptions were found to be inappropriate. Of those inappropriate, 68.6% were prescribed for primary prevention of cardiovascular disease (refer to table 4).

Table 4 – Expediency of the antiplatelet prescriptions, prevalence of inappropriate prescriptions and the reasons for inappropriateness

Antiplatelet prescription	Reason	n (%)
Appropriate		26 (42.6%)
Inappropriate		35 (57.4%)
Monotherapy	Primary prevention	24/35 (68.6%)
	Candidate for dual antiplatelets	1/35 (2.9%)
Dual therapy	More than recommended duration	10/35 (28.6%)

The price of an aspirin tablet was Rs 1.234 and a clopidogrel tablet was Rs 3.4 for 2023. About 0.71% of the institutional pharmaceutical budget in 2023 (Rs 3270679.26) had been allocated for antiplatelet agents. Of the quota that was allocated to antiplatelet agents (Rs 43837.96) nearly 53% was spent on inappropriate antiplatelet prescriptions (refer to table 5).

Table 5 – Calculation of the unwarranted cost incurred from inappropriate antiplatelet prescriptions and its burden on the institutional pharmaceutical budget

	Total number of patients on antiplatelet agent (n1)	Cost of antiplatelet agent per tablet for 2023 in Rs (b)	Annual requirement (n1*365)	Annual cost for 2023 in Rs (n1*365 *b)	Number of patients on inappropriate prescription (n2)	Inappropriate consumption of Aspirin (n2*365)	Unwarranted cost of Aspirin borne by the institution (n2*365*b)
Aspirin	56	1.234	20440	25222.96	24	8760	10809.84
Clopidogrel	15	3.4	5475	18615	10	3650	12410.00
Total annual budget allocation for antiplatelet agents 2023				43837.9	Total unwarranted cost		23219.84
				6			

Institutional pharmaceutical budget for 2023 in Rs (A)	Total budget allocation for antiplatelet agents 2023 in Rs (B)	Total unwarranted cost of antiplatelet agents In Rs (C)	Unwarranted burden on total pharmaceutical budget [(C/A)*100]	Unwarranted burden on budget allocation for antiplatelet agents [(C/B)*100]
3270679.26	43837.96	23219.84	0.71%	53.00%

Discussion

There are no studies conducted on the appropriateness of antiplatelet therapy in the PMCU setup in Sri Lanka. However, findings from a Sri Lankan study exploring a similar theme conducted in the medical clinic at a tertiary care institution in 2019 resonate with this study's finding that the principal reason for inappropriate prescription of antiplatelets is primary prevention.(24) The same study also demonstrates that the majority on these inappropriate prescriptions belong to the elderly, which is similar to the finding of this study. Findings from an Italian multicentre study conducted in the setting of a nursing home in 2020(25) and a study published in 2017(26) based on data from the REPOSI register (a register collecting information on drug prescription in patients aged ≥ 65 years from internal medicine and geriatric wards of Italian Hospitals) reiterate the inappropriate prescription of antiplatelets for primary prevention, especially among the elderly. There are no local or international studies exploring the financial burden/impact of inappropriate antiplatelet prescriptions.

This study sheds light on and emphasises a few key ideas:

- 1. Two-fold public risk:** The first risk is of course is to the health of the public. It should be appreciated that by virtue of their medical conditions and demographic factors such as age and sex, they are **already at a high baseline** for risk of bleeding. As evidenced in this study, majority (90%) of the patients on antiplatelet therapy were elderly patients with multimorbidity experiencing polypharmacy (80.3%). Antiplatelet therapy is just one factor that

predisposes to bleeding. Prescribing antiplatelets therefore, **adds** to an existent risk. Lack of judiciousness in prescribing antiplatelets increases the bleeding risk of a vulnerable population giving rise to undue morbidity and mortality.

Although free at the point of delivery, the Sri Lankan healthcare is funded by the tax payers' money. When put in due perspective it is obvious that the public funds their own healthcare. Hence it is pertinent to observe that injudicious prescribing predisposes the public not only to health risks but to an imperceptible financial risk.

2. The two-fold burden on state healthcare: The two-fold burden on state healthcare is reciprocal to the two-fold public risk.

Undue morbidity and mortality caused by injudicious prescription of antiplatelets utilises considerable state health resources used in service delivery. This causes strain on human and physical resources and diverts them from other essential services.

There is unnecessary strain on the state healthcare budget to accommodate patients on inappropriate antiplatelet prescriptions. A grassroot level picture is demonstrated in this study in the context of a PMCU. Here the burden on the institutional pharmaceutical budget is 0.71% but, of the quota allocated for aspirin nearly 53% amounts to inappropriate prescriptions.

The opportunity cost incurred by the state due to resources consumed by the undue morbidity and mortality caused of injudicious prescription of antiplatelets should also be appreciated.

3. The need for structured medication review: The import of medication review has been studied and recognised worldwide.(27–29) Medication reviews are conducted for patients on long-term medical follow up, to decide whether to prescribe, stop, escalate or de-escalate treatment, taking into account the patient's evolving clinical condition. Although structured

medication reviews are a part of quality control programmes in developed countries especially in the context of primary care(28), in Sri Lanka it is yet to be incorporated into standard practice. However, the opportunity for such review has been recognised in the published literature.(30)

The routine medical clinic visits of patients on long-term follow up yield an opportunity for review of both medicine and clinical condition of the patient. It is observed that this opportunity is not given the due importance and is therefore often missed. The high demand on the medical officers' time by the large volumes of patients who visit these state sector clinics often result in rushed, suboptimal consultations, leaving little room for in depth review of medicines. Reviewing medicine, as a result, is haphazard and limited to personal practice preferences of clinicians, their level of motivation and awareness on the need for such review.

A large number of patients followed up at medical clinics receives antiplatelet therapy. A considerable proportion of them are elderly patients with multimorbidity and hence at high risk of bleeding. It is therefore vital that the prescriptions of these patients are duly reviewed and optimised. Unfortunately, due to the aforementioned reasons, such review and optimisation is not done effectively and inappropriate prescriptions of antiplatelets are observed.

- 4. The need to keep up with the guidelines:** DAPT and MAPT are a result of evidenced based practice. The growing body of evidence is synthesised into practice guidelines by experts to optimise patient care. But it should be appreciated that new evidence can refute the old, calling for a change in practice. This has been the case with use of aspirin for primary prevention (refer to table 1).

New practices are introduced to healthcare staff by means of health ministry circulars and briefing meetings. However, there appears to be a delay in translating new knowledge to practice. It is the duty of responsible authorities (administrators, clinicians, professional

bodies) to establish innovative means of implementing newly communicated practices to circumvent such delay.

Conclusion

Delay in translating guidelines to practice and lack of medication review may have caused inappropriate prescription of antiplatelet agents placing patients at undue health risks and causing a financial risk to the healthcare system. Both clinicians and administrators should bear responsibility and strive to pre-empt health hazards and associated opportunity cost.

Recommendations

Prompt translation of updated knowledge to practice and conducting structured medication reviews come forth as the two ways of addressing the issues discussed above. Administrators should assume a more proactive role in addressing the non-clinical implications of this seemingly clinical problem by advocating clinical audits and 'best practice' initiatives at institutional level.

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